

Seasonal Thyroid Hormone Fluctuations

As a Candidate Cause of a Global SARS-CoV-2 Peak

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Figure 1- From Google.com, On 17 Aug 2021

From 52 days before 17 August 2021 (i.e. from 26 and 27 June), the incidence of SARS-CoV-2 Cases in the following areas has been rising simultaneously and before that it was either constant or declining: Iran, USA, Germany, Netherlands, France, Spain, Italy, Australia and the whole world.

The secretion of some thyroid hormones appears to decrease in summer [1], and the 26 June was almost the beginning of summer in the middle latitudes of the northern hemisphere. According to previous findings [2], a decrease in thyroid hormone apparently causes vulnerability to the severe form of SARS-CoV-2. Therefore, this coordination in the COVID-19 peak in these areas can be considered as a possible evidence of the effect of thyroid hormone levels on the severity of SARS-CoV-2.

References

- [1] Wang, Danchen, Songlin Yu, Yutong Zou, Honglei Li, Xinqi Cheng, Ling Qiu, and Tengda Xu. "Data mining: Seasonal fluctuations and associations between thyroid stimulating hormone and lipid profiles." *Clinica Chimica Acta* 506 (2020): 122-128.
- [2] Mohammad Reza Besharati, Nafiseh Jafari, Ehsan Mostafavi, Mohammad Izadi, & Alireza Talebpour. (2021). A Hypothesis about the Cause of Fatal Outcomes in SARS-Cov-2 (Version 11). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5169005>